

x-science Metadata Schema

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1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction to x-science

x-science (<https://x-science.org>), the data repository developed as part of the x-hub project¹, has been online since December 2018. x-hub, is a joint project of the OVGU Magdeburg, the University of Vienna, and the GESIS Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences with the cooperation partner University of Passau. The service is aimed at all experimental research projects from sociology, political science, psychology, and economics with any research paradigm background, and enables user-friendly archiving and retrieval. Another important goal of the repository is to make the data accessible and understandable across domain boundaries.

The creation of the repository x-science was preceded by the development of the repository x-econ. x-econ is aimed exclusively at archiving, making available, and re-using experimental game theory data from experimental economic research.

The main idea of the x-science repository is to create a single repository solution for all possible experimental paradigms in the social sciences (including experimental economics). x-science is the first step towards the transdisciplinary reuse of data in the experimental social sciences.

The present documentation is based primarily on da|ra 4.0^{2 3 4}, and the *x-econ Metadata Schema*⁵ and lists and describes the metadata elements, used to describe research information.

The present documentation is primarily based on da|ra 4.0 xxx and the x-econ metadata schema and lists and defines the metadata elements used to describe research information.

1.2 Goals and functionality

Following aspects were essential in the development of x-science:

- The primary goal is to provide user-friendly access for archiving and retrieving data from different experimental paradigms in the social sciences. Finding a solution for easy accessibility was challenging. To ensure a high level of usability, the first user interface (UI) prompts the data provider to indicate what discipline she comes from and what type of experiment she would like to archive data from. Based on these two decisions, a UI is displayed with metadata tailored to the user's needs.
- Experience from setting up x-econ helped to create the x-science metadata fields. As a consequence, the UI design and metadata fields for data drawn from the game-theoretic economics paradigm were taken over from x-econ.

¹ x-hub GEPRIIS DFG

² Koch, U., Akdeniz, E., Meichsner, J., Hausstein, B., & Harzenetter, K. (2017). da|ra Metadata Schema. Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Social and Economic Data. Version 4.0. GESIS Papers 2017|25. Köln: GESIS. doi: 10.4232/10.mdsdoc.4.0

³ <https://www.da-ra.de>

⁴ Helbig, K., Hausstein, B., Koch, U., Meichsner, J., & Kempf, A.O. (2014). da|ra Metadata Schema: Version 3.1. GESIS - Technical Reports 2014|17. Köln: GESIS. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4232/10.mdsdoc.3.1>

⁵ Betz, D., Biniossek, C., Wypior, H., Klas, C.-P., & Tavakolpoursaleh, N. (2022). Metadata Schema x-econ Repository. FEMM-Workingpaper Series. Magdeburg: OVGU

- A one-to-one adoption of metadata elements of existing metadata schemas in the social sciences such as datorium⁶ was not appropriate because the experimental social sciences use substantially different technical terms than empirical survey research. Even supposedly similar categories cannot be used in the same way in the context of global standardization (DDI-CDI, Dublin core). In these cases, new metadata elements had to be developed. As with x-econ, the x-science infrastructure intends to provide users low-threshold access.
- A DOI-reference, assigned by da|ra, enables immediate citation of the dataset. The experience of many researchers with the DOI-registration of their literature publications is built on and extended here.
- The mandatory fields required for DOI registration, based on the DDI standard, are adopted from da|ra and supplemented by some additional metadata fields developed based on expert discussions.
- The development of the x-science metadata schema is based on the needs of the research community. Consistent with x-econ, the minimal x-science metadata schema (mandatory fields) was designed for comprehensive archiving of all experimental social science research datasets (input maximization), while the more detailed metadata schema was created for in-depth reuse (output maximization). Data providers themselves decide on the depth of documentation of their data.

Purpose and location of x-science:

- As part of the x-hub project: x-science is the first repository for data from the experimental social sciences after x-econ, comprising economics, sociology, political sciences, and psychology.
- x-science meets the function of the minimal and optimal archiving standard.

1.3 Technical Basis

Technically, x-science runs on a Linux-Server with Ubuntu⁷ as a virtual machine (VM) in the network architecture of GESIS. To create the repository x-science, DSpace⁸ is used as an open-source repository software package. DSpace is a free software for running document servers, written in Java and JSP and using a relational database. DSpace was selected because this document storage software is used broadly accepted in the scientific community, and GESIS already has extensive experience with DSpace. In addition, DSpace provides internal, collaborative curation workflows to communicate between curators and with the submitter of research data to foster qualitative research metadata.

The UI is the only visible interface of the x-hub portals for the researchers and is displayed according to current standards and design options. Particular user requirements were not technically feasible with DSpace 5. Thus, the Vaadin-Framework⁹ was used as system with a modular architecture newly developed for x-hub, which allows for a more flexible and efficient configuration, as well as more user-friendly portals.

For the development of the server architecture of x-science, the software Git¹⁰ is used on the

⁶ Jensen, U., & Linne, M. (2017). SowiDataNet - Metadatenschema Version 1.0. GESIS Papers, 2017|28. Köln: GESIS. doi: 10.21241/ssoar.54975

⁷ <https://www.ubuntu.com>

⁸ <http://dspace.org>

⁹ <http://dspace.org>

¹⁰ <https://git-scm.com>

programming side, for distributed version management of files. This is facilitated by GitLab¹¹, a web version control application for software projects based on Git. GitLab also used to manage tasks between managers, developers, and testers (agile software development).

1.3.1 Modular Architecture

x-science builds on the same new modular architecture as x-econ, which on the one hand is more flexible and efficient in development, operation, and maintainability, and on the other hand, can adapt to user requirements to provide a user-friendly portal.

This modular architecture (see Figure 1) is structured as follows. The data repository is stored with a current DSpace version. DSpace provides decoupled access to workflows and data via a REST interface. By using this REST-interface, the UI can be implemented outside of DSpace by modern UI frameworks such as AngularJS or Vaadin. In x-hub, the Vaadin framework was selected based on an internal evaluation. By modularizing data storage and UI, it is possible to replace the previously used DSpace with other repository software, such as DataVerse. This means that the service is adaptable and sustainable. Another component is an Elasticsearch that can be used for general search.

Figure 1: Modular architecture

The implemented portals (x-econ and x-science) differ in the following criteria: the underlying metadata schema and the portal layout. By using the new UI framework and the REST interface, these criteria can be implemented efficiently.

The x-hub portals consist of one user interface component, each for x-econ and x-science, several service components, and only one DSpace instance. Both portals are thus supported by the same DSpace instance. In addition, both portals have been connected to da|ra for the assignment of persistent identifiers (DOI); the long-term archiving of data and metadata takes place in the GESIS data archive.

1.4 Transdisciplinarity

Several structural elements of a transdisciplinary metadata schema have been implemented

¹¹ <https://gitlab.com>

in x-science. Thus, the data provider can decide in two steps via the pre-selection UI from which research discipline and experiment type the data to be archived originate. Only the metadata corresponding to the data collection method that is used, is presented to the data provider in a unified interface. The x-science metadata schema enables deep documentation of a multitude of social sciences experiment types. These metadata elements were developed in collaboration with researchers and are a first step in making the data accurately available across disciplines. In future versions of x-science, it is planned to include additional structural elements of the transdisciplinary metadata schema.

1.5 New UI in x-science: The preselection UI – the switch

x-science proposes a newly developed user interface - the switch - to address the research landscape in the social sciences, which includes several research paradigms across different disciplines, but also to reduce thresholds (and required input time). The purpose of the switch is that before accessing the actual metadata schema to document the dataset, the data provider must first specify from which scientific discipline and experimental paradigm the data to be archived originate. Thus, the data provider must first select an entry from a list of the following entries (only one entry possible):

- Behavioral economics
- Behavioral finance
- Behavioral public finance
- Experimental economics
- Experimental finance
- Experimental macro economics
- Experimental political science
- Experimental public finance
- Experimental social science
- Experimental sociology
- Other experimental science

Finally, the data provider has to decide from which exact experiment type the data originate and choose between (multiple entries possible):

- Game theoretic experiment (laboratory)
- Game theoretic experiment (field experiment)
- Laboratory experiment (general)
- Field experiment (general)
- Experimental survey
- Factorial survey - conjoint analysis
- Method experiment
- Survey (quantitative)
- Survey (qualitative)
- Show all metadata

In the experiment type UI, it is possible to select all options simultaneously. This enables x-science to document a wide range of (future) combinations of experimental paradigms. See here two screenshots of the user interface:

Enter your dataset

Enter your data and files to your dataset. If you prefer, you can save it and return at any time to work on it again.

! Please select your experimental paradigm and the relevant metadata:

Scientific discipline

Other experimental science ▼

Show metadata for

Game theoretic experiment (laboratory)

Game theoretic experiment (field experiment)

Laboratory experiment (general)

Field experiment (general)

Experimental survey

Factorial survey- conjoint analysis

Method experiment

Survey (quantitative)

Survey (qualitative)

Show all metadata

Select

Figure 2: Preselection UI for choosing the experimental paradigm

Enter your dataset

Enter your data and files to your dataset. If you prefer, you can save it and return at any time to work on it again.

! Please select your experimental paradigm and the relevant metadata:

Scientific discipline

Other experimental science ▼

- Behavioral economics
- Behavioral finance
- Behavioral public finance
- Experimental economics
- Experimental finance
- Experimental macro economics
- Experimental political science
- Experimental public finance
- Experimental social science
- Experimental sociology
- Other experimental science

Survey (quantitative)

Survey (qualitative)

Show all metadata

Select

Figure 3: Preselection UI for choosing the discipline

2 Metadata schema

The purpose of the x-science metadata schema is to provide a meaningful description of each dataset based on structured metadata to document, search, and cite archived materials.

To cover the field of experiments in the social sciences as comprehensively as possible, the metadata schema of x-econ was integrated into x-science. Supplementary metadata fields were created in collaboration with experts from the respective fields. A substantial part of x-science is assigned to metadata describing factorial surveys. These metadata fields were jointly developed with Thomas Hinz and his staff, Stefanie Eifler, Knut Petzold, and Hermann Dülmer, whom we would like to thank here for their contribution.

2.1 x-science metadata

The following tables provide a detailed description of all metadata elements that must (mandatory elements) or can (recommended elements) be specified when uploading research information to x-science. Mandatory elements are marked with M. However, data providers are generally advised to fill in as many fields as possible.

All metadata are provided in English only. Data providers should provide metadata information in English.

The metadata schema of x-science follows the structure of the metadata schema da|ra version 4.0.

The attribute Occurrence (Occ) specifies how many instances an element can have:

0-n = optional and repeatable (element may not occur at all (0), once, or several times)

0-1 = optional, but not repeatable (element may not occur at all or once)

1-n = necessary and repeatable (element must occur once (1) and can occur several times)

1 = necessary, but not repeatable (element must occur exactly once (1))

There exist several administrative elements for quality assurance and control of each publication. If a publication is reported, the curators are informed by email. Two curators check the data publication and manually approve it. Only then the data publication is visible in x-science.org. The visibility of the dataset itself depends on the embargo that was chosen by the data provider.

2.2 x- science metadata schema

Legend

Container	=	Contains thematically related metadata
M	=	Required/Mandatory (M)
Designation	=	Designation in Web-Interface of x-science
x-science sequence	=	No. 0 to 99 da ra sequences; No. 100 to 199 – newly added x-econ metadata; No. 200 to 299 – newly added x-science metadata

Table 1: x-science metadata schema part I – *preselection UI*

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
200		selectParadigm	Container element to provide information about the relevant research paradigm the archived dataset comes from.	M	1	Please select your experimental paradigm and the relevant metadata:
200.1		scientificDiscipline	The scientific discipline the dataset comes from.	M	1	Scientific discipline See 2.3.1 Controlled list: Scientific Discipline
200.2		showMetadata	Selection of metadata that corresponds to data that will be uploaded.	M	1-n	Show metadata for See 2.3.2 Controlled list: Show metadata for

Table 2: x-science metadata schema – part II

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
1	1	resourceType	Predefined terms to provide information about the type of resource being registered to differentiate between registered resources.	M	1	See 2.3.3 Controlled list: Resource Type (from da ra controlled list descriptionType appendix 4.1.4 for definitions ¹² . Here only “5. Others”).
3	3	resourceIdentifier	Container element for a resource identifier, which includes a unique identifier and a version number to identify the resource.		0-1	
3.1	3.1	identifier	The identifier is a unique internal value for the registered resource provided by the publication agent to disambiguate between resources.		1	Example: database ID
3.2	3.2	currentVersion	A version number, which is a unique sequence of numbers, can be provided for the registered resource as		0-1	Example: Version 1.0.0

¹² Koch, U., Akdeniz, E., Meichsner, J., Hausstein, B., & Harzenetter, K. (2017). da|ra Metadata Schema. Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Social and Economic Data. Version 4.0. GESIS Papers 2017|25. Köln: GESIS. doi: 10.4232/10.mdsdoc.4.0

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
			a reference that changes have been made between different versions.			
4	4	titles	Container element to provide language-dependent information about the main titles of the registered resource.		1	
4.1	4.1	title	Container element for one specific language dependent title.		1-n	
4.1.2	4.1.2	titleName	A name or title of the registered resource.	M	1	Title of this dataset
7	7	creators	Container element to provide information about a person, e.g., researchers involved in producing the registered resource or an institution responsible for the substantive and/or intellectual content of the registered resource.		1	Authors
7.1	7.1	creator	Container element to provide information about a person (author)		1-n	Other than in da ra 4.0 only person is allowed.
7.1.1	7.1.1	person	Container element to provide information about a person (author).		1	
7.1.1.1 and 7.1.1.2	7.1.1.1	firstName and middleName	The first name of a person (author) and the middle name of a person (author).	M	1	First name
7.1.1.3	7.1.1.3	lastName	The last name of a person (author).	M	1	Last name
100.1		emailAddress	The e-mail address of a person (author)	M	1	E-mail
7.1.1.4	7.1.1.4	personIDs	Container element to provide information about a unique identifier of the person and the name of the schema identifier to disambiguate individuals of similar names.		0-1	
7.1.1.4.1	7.1.1.4.1	personID	Container element to provide information about a person's unique identifier.		1-n	Several personIDs may be provided.
7.1.1.4.1.1	7.1.1.4.1.1	identifierURI	Person ID: The value of a formally registered unique identifier.		1	Persistent Identifier Unique persistent identifier of the author Example: ISNI ID: 5859 1764 (Heiko Peters). (e.g., ORCID https://orcid.org , ISNI http://www.isni.org)
7.1.1.4.1.2	7.1.1.4.1.2	identifierSchema	The name of the schema the identifier is related to.	M if identifierURI is used	1	Examples: ORCID, VIAF, GND, etc.
7.1.1.5	7.1.1.5	affiliation	Container element to provide information about the organizational or institutional connection of a person.		0-1	
7.1.1.5.1	7.1.1.5.1	affiliationName	The name of the organization or institution a person is affiliated to.		1	Institution/University A list with institutions is provided after the user fills in 3 letters.

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
8	8	dataURLs	Container element to provide information about the URL or URN (a reference to a web resource that specifies its location) linking to the registered resource.	M	1	
8.1	8.1	dataURL	An URL or URN (a reference to a web resource that specifies its location) linking to the registered resource.		1-n	Several dataURLs may be provided.
9	9	doiProposal	A persistent interoperable identifier (=DOI) a publication agent suggests for identification purposes of the registered resource.	M	0-1	DOI Valid DOI Syntax according the standard, see doi.org
10	10	publicationDate	Container element to provide information about the date the registered resource was published or is going to be published.	M	1	
10.1	10.1	date	The publication day, month and/or year of the registered resource submitted by the publication agent.		1	You may provide a complete calendar date.
13	13	availability	Container element to classify or describe availability conditions of the registered resource.			
13.3	13.3	embargoDate	Information about the end date of access restrictions in case an embargo period has been in effect.		0-1	Embargo Allowed value is a valid date expressed in the format DD-MM-YYYY-
14	14	rights	Container element to provide information about legal principles or fundamental normative rules about what is allowed of people or owed to people in regards to the registered resource.	M	1	
14.1	14.1	licenseType	License. Predefined terms to provide information about different types of creative commons licenses to allow creators to maintain copyrights on their works and clarify what others can do with content licensed with one of those licenses.		1	License See 2.3.4 Controlled list: License Type Detail
17	17	classifications	Container element to provide information about a multidisciplinary or discipline-specific system for hierarchical classifications. At the same time, classifications branch out into the special knowledge areas out of a few main compartments.		0-1	

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
17.1	17.1	classification	Container element for internal and external classifications.		1-n	
17.1.1	17.1.1	classificationInternal	Container element for the internal classification system provided by da ra (Classifications: Journal of Economic Literature (JEL), ZA, GESIS).		0-1	
17.1.1.1	17.1.1.1	schema	The name of the internal schema used to differentiate between classification systems describing the topical coverage of the registered resource.		1	JEL (Journal of Economic Literature) Classification; GESIS Classification for the Social Sciences; Library of Congress Classification Scheme: Social Science; APA PsycINFO Classification
17.1.1.2	17.1.1.2	identifiers	Container element to provide information about the unique identifier of the internal schema.		1	
17.1.1.2.1	17.1.1.2.1	identifier	The identifier is a unique internal value of the internal schema to disambiguate classification systems. JEL Code (Journal of Economic Literature)		1-n	JEL code (Journal of Economic Literature) https://www.aea-web.org/econlit/jel-Codes.php?view=jel Example: C92, D44
17.1.1.2.1	17.1.1.2.1	identifier	The identifier is a unique internal value of the internal schema to disambiguate classification systems. GESIS Classification for the Social Sciences		1-n	GESIS Classification for the Social Sciences See 2.3.5 Controlled list: GESIS Classification for the Social Sciences
17.1.1.2.1	17.1.1.2.1	identifier	The identifier is a unique internal value of the internal schema to disambiguate classification systems. Library of Congress Classification Scheme: Social Science		1-n	Library of Congress Classification Scheme See 2.3.6 Controlled list: Library of Congress Classification Scheme
17.1.1.2.1	17.1.1.2.1	identifier	The identifier is a unique internal value of the internal schema to disambiguate classification systems. APA PsycINFO Classification		1-n	APA PsycINFO Classification See 2.3.7 Controlled list: APA PsycINFO Classification
17.1.2	17.1.2	classificationExternal	Container element to provide language-dependent information about a classification system provided by the publication agent.		0-1	
17.1.2.2	17.1.2.2	classificationSchema	Game Classification: Game theoretic classification of the experiment.		1	The name of the external schema used to differentiate between classification systems a publication agent provides to describe the topical coverage.
17.1.2.3	17.1.2.3	terms	Container element to provide information about the subject class.		1	
17.1.2.3.1	17.1.2.3.1	term	The subject class from the external classification system a publication agent	M if	1-n	Game classification See 2.3.8 Controlled list: Game Classification

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
			uses to describe the topical coverage.	classificationSchema is used		
101.1		classification- Others	Free-text field to provide further classification information.		0-n	Further classification information that is not included in the controlled list.
101.3		topicSpecification	Topic specification of research data and the area of application.		0-n	Topic specification See 2.3.9 Controlled list: Topic Specification
102.1		designDecisions	Information about the experimental design.		0-n	Design decisions See 2.3.17 Controlled list: Design decisions
102.2		Incentive	Information about the incentives used in the experiment.		0-n	Incentives See 2.3.19 Controlled list: Incentive
102.3		interaction	Information about the interaction type in the experiment.		0-n	Interactions See 2.3.18 Controlled list: Interaction
102.4		professional- StatusParticipants	General classification of participants professional status (e.g., students)		0-n	Professional status of participants See 2.3.14 Controlled list: Professional Status of Participants
102.5		rounds	Number of rounds played in the experiment.		0-1	Rounds
102.6		ExperimentalSoftware	Software used in the experiment.		0-n	Experimental Software Example: z-Tree, classEx See 2.3.13 Controlled list: Experimental Software
102.6.1		experimentalSoftwareFree text	A free-text field to describe the software used in the experiment.		0-n	
102.7		earningsRange	Container element to provide information about the earnings range in the experiment.		0-1	Earnings range in the experiment
102.7.1		minimum	The lowest income in the experiment.		0-1	Minimum of earnings range
102.7.2		maximum	The highest income in the experiment.		0-1	Maximum of earnings range
102.7.3		mean	The mean income in the experiment.		0-1	Mean of earnings range Example: Euro, Dollar
102.8		currency	The currency used to describe the earnings range.	M if minimum, maximum or mean is used	1	Currency of earnings range Example: Euro, US Dollar S See 2.3.15 Controlled list: Currency
102.9		showUpFee	Container element to provide information about the show-up fee of the participants in the experiment.		0-1	Show-up fee
102.9.1		amount	The amount of the show-up fee.		0-1	Amount
102.10		ageRange	Container element to provide information about the age range of participants.		0-1	
102.10.1		minimum	The youngest age.		0-1	Minimum

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
						Value >= 1 and <= 140
102.10.2		maximum	The oldest age.		0-1	Maximum Value >= 1 and <= 140
102.10.3		mean	The mean age.		0-1	Mean Value >= 1 and <= 140
18	18	controlledKeywords	Container element to provide information about a classification of the terminology to classify or index the registered resource.		0-1	
18.1	18.1	controlledKeyword	Container element for controlled keywords.		1-n	
18.1.1	18.1.1	keywordSchemaType	The name of the internal schema used to differentiate between keywords to describe the topical coverage.		1	Content: x-econ keywords of experimental economics
18.1.2	18.1.2	identifiers	Container element to provide information on a unique identifier of the internal schema.		1	
18.1.2.1	18.1.2.1	identifier	Keywords of experimental economics related to the data.		1-n	Keywords See 2.3.10 Controlled list: Keywords
19	19	freeKeywords	Container element to provide language-dependent information about the content of the registered resource if the controlled list of classifications cannot provide enough information.		1-n	
19.1.3.1	19.1.3.1	keyword	A textual description or terminology to describe the content of the registered resource.		1-n	
20	20	descriptions	Container element to provide language-dependent information, statements or passages that give additional details about someone or something.		0-1	
20.1	20.1	description	Description of the resource content.		1	
20.1.2	20.1.2	freetext	Additional information about the registered resource.		1	Description of this dataset
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
20.1	20.1	description	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
201.20.1.2	20.1.2	methodologicalFrameworkFreetext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other		1	Methodological Framework Description of the methodological framework under which the data

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
			categories. May be used for technical information.			were collected.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
20.1	20.1	description	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
103.20.1.2	20.1.2	theoreticalFrameworkFreetext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Theoretical framework Example: Research from previous literature used to derive and test the hypotheses in the experiment.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
21	21	geographicCoverages	Container element to provide geographical information of the data collection including a controlled vocabulary and a free-text field.		0-1	
21.1	21.1	geographicCoverage	Container element to provide information about the geographic coverage of the registered resource.		1-n	
21.1.2	21.1.2	geographicCoveragesFree	Container element to provide language-dependent information about the geographic coverage.		0-1	
21.1.2.1	21.1.2.1	geographicCoverageFree	Container element for a language-dependent free-text field to provide geographical information.		1-n	
21.1.2.1.2	21.1.2.1.2	freetext	A free text field to describe the locations or spatial regions covered by the data.		1	Geographic Coverage
21.1	21.1	geographicCoverage	Container element to provide information about the geographic coverage of the registered resource.		1-n	
21.1.1	21.1.1	geographicCoverageControlled	Predefined terms to provide geographical information to differentiate between different locations the experiment was conducted.		0-1	Laboratory of experiment(s) See 2.3.12 Controlled list: Laboratory
104.21.1.2.1.2	21.1.2.1.2	LaboratoryOfExperimentsFreetext	A free-text field to describe the location of the laboratory in case it cannot be found in the controlled vocabulary list.			Further information on Laboratory of experiments that is not included in the controlled list.
22	22	universes	Container element to provide language-dependent		0-1	For example, a population could consist of all

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
			information about statistical entities about which inferences are to be drawn and to which analytic results refer.			the persons in the country, or those in a particular geographical location, or a special ethnic group, depending on the purpose and coverage of the study.
22.1	22.1	universe	Container element for one specific language dependent description about the universe to which analytic results refer.		1-n	
20.2.1	22.1.2	sampled	Description of the statistical entities of the survey.		1-n	Participant pool Description of the population, from which the participants in the experiment were drawn. Example: All persons in the laboratory participant pool
23	23	samplings	Container element to provide language-dependent information about the sample and sample design used to select the survey respondents to represent the population.		0-1	
23.1	23.1	sampling	Container element for one specific language dependent sampling method.		1-n	
23.1.2	23.1.2	method	The type of sample and sample design used to select the respondents to represent the population.		1	Sampling method
202.20	20	factorialSurveysDescriptions	Container element to provide language-dependent information, statements or passages that give additional details about someone or something.		0-1	
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.1.20.1.2	20.1.2	respondentsConstantFreertext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Percentage of respondents with constant answers Free-text field to state the number of respondents with constant answers.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.2.20.1.2	20.1.2	randomisationProcedureFreertext	All additional information about the registered resource		1	Randomization Procedure Free-text field to describe the randomization

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
			that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.			procedure.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.3.20.1.2	20.1.2	independentVariableFreetext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Independent Variable(s) Free-text field to describe the independent variable(s) in the experiment.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.4.20.1.2	20.1.2	dependentVariableFreetext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Dependent Variable(s) Free-text field to describe the dependent variable(s) in the experiment.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.5.20.1.2	20.1.2	experimentalStimulusFreetext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Experimental Stimulus See 2.3.16 Controlled list: Experimental Stimulus Description of the experimental stimulus in the experiment.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.6.20.1.2	20.1.2	specificationStimulusFreetext	All additional information about the registered resource		1	Specification of the experimental stimulus Free-text field to specify the experimental

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
			that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.			stimulus in the experiment.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.7.20.1.2	20.1.2	PretestFreetext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Pretest Free-text field to describe the pretest procedure.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.8.20.1.2	20.1.2	HypothesisFreetext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Hypothesis Free-text field to state the hypothesis in the experiment.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.9.20.1.2	20.1.2	numberConfederatesFreetext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Number of confederates Free-text field to state the number of confederates in the experiment (if applicable).
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.10.2.0.1.2	20.1.2	experimentalSettingFreetext	All additional information about the registered resource		1	Description of the experimental setting Free-text field to describe the experimental

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
			that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.			setting of the experiment.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.11.2 0.1.2	20.1.2	dimensionsNumberFreeText	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Number of dimensions (factors) A free-text field to state the number of dimensions used to describe the vignettes.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.12.2 0.1.2	20.1.2	factorLevelsFreeText	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Factor levels A free-text field to define and describe the number of levels used.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.13.2 0.1.2	20.1.2	procedureIllogicalVignettesFreeText	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Procedure with illogical vignettes A free-text field to describe the procedures you performed with illogical combinations.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.14.2 0.1.2	20.1.2	estimatedEffectsFreeText	All additional information about the registered resource		1	Estimated effects See 2.3.23 Controlled list: Estimated Effects Predefined terms to

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
			that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.			provide information about all estimated main and interaction effects.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.15.2 0.1.2	20.1.2	construction-VignetteSample-Freetext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Construction of vignette sample See 2.3.24 Controlled list Construction Vignette Sample Predefined terms to describe the procedure to construct the vignette sample.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.16.2 0.1.2	20.1.2	dEfficiencyFreetext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	D-efficiency A free-text field to provide information about the value for the d-efficiency (for qualitative data only).
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.17.2 0.1.2	20.1.2	numberVignettesPerson-Freetext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Number of vignettes per person (set size) A free-text field to state the number of vignettes per person (set size).
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
202.18.2 0.1.2	20.1.2	presentationOrderFreertext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Presentation order See 2.3.25 Controlled list Presentation Order Predefined terms to state the presentation order.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.19.2 0.1.2	20.1.2	vignettePresentationFreertext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Vignette presentation See 2.3.26 Controlled list Vignette Presentation Predefined terms to describe the presentation of vignettes.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.20.2 0.1.2	20.1.2	minmumNumberJudgementsFreertext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Minimum number of judgements per vignette A free-text field to state the minimum number of judgements.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.21.2 0.1.2	20.1.2	answerScaleRatingFreertext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Answer scale rating See 2.3.27 Controlled list Answer Scale Rating Predefined terms to describe the answer scale rating
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
202.22.2 0.1.2	20.1.2	numberCategoriesPonitScale-Freetext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	If point scale: how many categories? A free-text field to state the number of categories (point scale).
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
202.20.1	20.1	factorialSurveysDescription	Container element for language-dependent descriptions.		1-n	
202.23.2 0.1.2	20.1.2	answerScaleRankingFreetext	All additional information about the registered resource that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.		1	Answer scale ranking A free-text field to describe the ranking of the answering scale.
20.1.3	20.1.3	descriptionType	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of descriptions used to describe the registered resource.		1	See 2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type
24	24	temporalCoverages	Container element to provide information about the time frame of the data collection.		0-1	
24.1	24.1	temporalCoverage	Container element to provide structured or unstructured information about the time frame of the data collection.		1-n	
24.1.1	24.1.1	temporalCoverage-Formal	Container element to provide information about the structured temporal time frame of the data collection.		0-1	
105.1.24.1.1.1	24.1.1.1	startDate	Container element that provide information about the start date of the data collection.			
105.1.1.2 4.1.1.1.1	24.1.1.1 1	date	The date the experiments started.		1	Period of experiments from "From" as date: YYYY-MM-DD
105.2.24.1.1.2	24.1.1.2	endDate	Container element that provides information about the end date of the experiments.		0-1	
105.2.1.2 4.1.1.2.1	24.1.1.2 1	date	The date the experiments ended.		1	Period of experiments to "To" as date: YYYY-MM-DD
28	28	collectionModes	Container element to provide information about the mode of data collection used to collect information from a sample in an experiment.		0-1	

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
28.1	28.1	collectionMode	Container element to provide structured or unstructured information about the mode of data collection used to collect information from a sample in a survey.		1-n	
28.1.1	28.1.1	collectionMode-Type	Predefined terms to provide information about different types of methods that are used to collect information from a sample in a survey.		0-1	Example: Paper questionnaire, Experiment, etc. See da ra controlled list 4.1.7 for definitions. Here only "22: Experiment"
28.1.2	28.1.2	collectionModes-Free	Container element to provide language-dependent information to classify or describe methods that are used to collect information from a sample in a survey.		0-1	
106.28.1.2.1	28.1.2.1	collectionMode-Free	Container element for language-dependent descriptions about the mode of data collection.		1-n	
106.1.28.1.2.1.2	28.1.2.1.2	collectionMode-FreeExp	An additional field to describe the methods that are used to collect information from a sample in a survey.		1-n	Data collection mode See 2.3.12 Controlled list: Data Collection Mode
106.1.1.28.1.2.1.2		collectionMode-FreeExpOthers	Further data collection mode information that is not included in the controlled list.		1-n	
29	29	dataSets	Container element to provide information about the dataset, which is a collection of data, where every column of the statistical data matrix represents a particular variable, and each row corresponds to a given member of the dataset in question.	M	0-1	
29.1	29.1	dataSet	Container element to provide information about a specific data set.		1-n	
29.1.2	29.1.2	unitType	Describes the entity being analyzed or observed in the resource.	Use only together with numberUnits.	0-1	See da ra controlled list appendix 4.1.8 for definitions. Here only „1: Individual “or „11: Group “. Use only together with numberUnits!
29.1.3	29.1.3	numberUnits	The number of units being analyzed or observed in the resource.	Use only together with unitType.	0-1	Total number of independent observations unitType has a contextual relationship with numberUnits. When a unitType is being selected, it is mandatory to provide a number of units and vice versa. Finally, it means that both together are mandatory;

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
						otherwise, none of them should be used.
107		totalNumberParticipants	The total number of participants being analyzed or observed in the resource.		0-1	Total number of participants Total number of participants in the experiment.
108		largestGroupSize	The largest group size of one relevant analyzed observation in resource.		0-1	Largest group size Example: a public good experiment with a largest group size of 10 participants in one single observation => 10
29.1.6	29.1.6	files	Container element to provide specific information of the data file.	M	0-1	
29.1.6.1	29.1.6.1	file	Container element to provide specific information of the data file such as name, format, size, and fingerprint of the file.		1-n	
29.1.6.1.1	29.1.6.1.1	name	The name of the data file.		0-1	Upload files (file name) Example: Dataset_xyz
109.1		fileType	The type of the data file.	M for Dataset	0-1	Type of data Example: Codebook, Dataset See 2.3.21 Controlled list: Type of Data
109.1.1		fileTag	Tag to provide specific information of the data file.		0-n	Add tags Example: Treatment x, Instruction, STATA 10.0
109.1.2		fileDescription	Description to provide specific information of the data file.		1	Description of this dataset
29.1.6.1.2	29.1.6.1.2	format	A textual description of the technical format of the data file.		0-1	Use file extension or MIME type where possible. Examples: application/x-stata, application/pdf
29.1.6.1.3	29.1.6.1.3	size	The size of a data file or resource.		0-1	Example: KB, MB
29.1.6.1.4	29.1.6.1.4	fingerprint	Checksum which confirms the authenticity of the data or data file by assigning a hash value (digital fingerprint).		0-1	
29.1.6.1.5	29.1.6.1.5	fingerprint-Method	The technical procedure generating a data fingerprint.		0-1	Example: MD5, SHA1
30	30	notes	Container element to provide language-dependent remarks or other information about the registered resource.		0-1	
110.30.1	30.1	note	Container element for one specific language-dependent further remark about the registered resource.		1	
110.1.30.1.2	30.1.2	text Leading question and object of data	Textual description of the leading research question and the object of data		1	Leading question and object of data collection

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
		collection	collection.			
32	32	publications	Container element to provide information about an article, a document, etc. that has been made available to the public.		0-1	
32.1	32.1	publication	Container element to provide information about a structured or/and unstructured information about a publication.		1-n	
32.1.1	32.1.1	structuredPublication	Container element to provide structured information about an article, a document or another resource that has been made available to the public.		1	
32.1.1.1	32.1.1.1	documentType	The type of publication that has been made available to the public to differentiate between document types.		0-1	Document type of publication See 2.3.22 Controlled list: Document Type
32.1.1.2	32.1.1.2	authorsEditors	Container element to provide information about a person, who wrote and originated (author) and/or edited and modified (editor) the publication.		1	
32.1.1.2.1	32.1.1.2.1	authorEditor	Container element to provide information about an author and/or an editor of a publication.		1-n	
32.1.1.2.1.1	32.1.1.2.1.1	author	Container element to provide information about an author.		0-1	
32.1.1.2.1.1.3	32.1.1.2.1.1.3	name	The full name of the author.		1	Author Includes firstName, middleName and lastName.
32.1.1.3	32.1.1.3	title	The title or name of the publication.		1	Title of publication
32.1.1.4	32.1.1.4	year	The year on which the publication has been or is planned to be published.		0-1	Year of publication
32.1.1.14	32.1.1.14	PIDs	Container element to provide information about the Persistent Identifier (PID) that has been generated to uniquely and permanently identify the structured publication.		0-1	It is used to be able to reference and retrieve data permanently. PIDs link data with the data producer or with research objects based on them.
32.1.1.14.1	32.1.1.14.1	PID	Container element for the value of a formally registered unique and persistent identifier of the structured information of publication.		1-n	
32.1.1.14	32.1.1.14	ID	The value of a formally		1-n	Link (URL)

x-science sequence	da ra sequence	Property	Definition	Function of element	Occ	Usage notes
.1.1	.1.1		registered unique and persistent identifier of the structured information of a publication.			
32.1.2	32.1.2	unstructured-Publication	Container element to provide unstructured information about an article, a document or another resource that has been made available to the public.		1	
32.1.2.1	32.1.2.1	freetext	Unstructured bibliographic information related to the publication.		1	Abstract
30	30	notes	Container element to provide remarks or other information about the registered resource.		0-1	
30.1	30.1	note	Container element for further remarks about the registered resource.		1-n	
30.1.2	30.1.2	text	Textual description of the contents of the dataset.		1	Further relevant information on the dataset (e.g., steps to reproduce or more information about your lab and the process of data collection)

2.3 Appendix: controlled vocabulary in x-science

Shown below are the controlled lists, which are used in x-science. This includes the adopted lists from da|ra for the mandatory fields and the new developed technical vocabulary for primary data of the experimental social sciences research. 1234

2.3.1 Controlled list: Scientific Discipline

Identifier	Type
1	Behavioral economics
2	Behavioral finance
3	Behavioral public finance
4	Experimental economics
5	Experimental finance
6	Experimental macro economics
7	Experimental political science
8	Experimental public finance
9	Experimental social science
10	Experimental sociology

11	Other experimental science
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2.3.2 Controlled list: Show metadata for

Identifier	Type
1	Game theoretic experiment (laboratory)
2	Game theoretic experiment (field experiment)
3	Laboratory experiment (general)
4	Field experiment (general)
5	Experimental survey
6	Factorial survey- conjoint analysis
7	Method experiment
8	Survey (quantitative)
9	Survey (qualitative)
10	Show all metadata

2.3.3 Controlled list: Resource Type¹³

Identifier	Type (en)	Definition
2	Dataset	Data encoded in a defined structure.

2.3.4 Controlled list: License Type Detail

Identifier	Type	Usage notes; Help text
1	Creative Commons Universal - CC0 - Public domain "no Copyright"	Corresponds to licenseType: 1 in da ra 4.0; The content underlies no restrictions ; the licensor (you) give permission to copy, modify and (re)distribute the data for any purpose, even for commercial purposes.
2	Creative Commons 4.0 International - by - Attribution	Corresponds to licenseType: 6 in da ra 4.0; The licensor (you) give permission to copy, modify and (re)distribute the data for any purpose, even for commercial purposes . However, the user must give appropriate credit , provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made .
3	Creative Commons 4.0 International - by-sa - Attribution ShareAlike	Corresponds to licenseType: 7 in da ra 4.0; The licensor (you) give permission to copy, modify and (re)distribute the data for any purpose, even for commercial purposes. However, the user must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. Furthermore, if you modify the material, you must distribute your contributions under the same license as the original.

¹³ Koch, U., Akdeniz, E., Meichsner, J., Hausstein, B., & Harzenetter, K. (2017). da|ra Metadata Schema. Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Social and Economic Data. Version 4.0. GESIS Papers 2017|25. Köln: GESIS. doi: 10.4232/10.mds-doc.4.0

4	Creative Commons 4.0 International - by-nd - Attribution NoDerivatives	Corresponds to licenseType: 5 in da ra 4.0; The licensor (you) give permission to copy and (re)distribute the data for any purpose in its original form, even for commercial purposes. Distribution of modified material is thus prohibited. Furthermore, you must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.
5	Creative Commons 4.0 International - by-nc - Attribution NonCommercial	Corresponds to licenseType: 3 in da ra 4.0; The licensor (you) give permission to copy, modify and (re)distribute the data only for non-commercial purposes. Furthermore, the user must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.
6	Creative Commons 4.0 International - by-nc-sa -Attribution NonCommercial ShareAlike	Corresponds to licenseType: 4 in da ra 4.0; The licensor (you) give permission to copy, modify and (re)distribute the data only for non-commercial purposes. However, the user must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. Furthermore, if you modify the material, you must distribute your contributions under the same license as the original.
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2.3.5 Controlled list: GESIS Classification for the Social Sciences

Identifier	Type	Identifier	Type	Identifier	Type
1	10000	54	10606	107	1090304
2	10101	55	10607	108	1090400
3	10102	56	10608	109	1090401
4	10103	57	10609	110	1090402
5	10104	58	10610	111	1090403
6	10105	59	10611	112	1090404
7	10199	60	10612	113	1090405
8	10200	61	10613	114	1090406
9	10201	62	10614	115	10905
10	10202	63	10615	116	10999
11	10203	64	10616	117	11000
12	10204	65	10617	118	11001
13	10205	66	10699	119	11002
14	10206	67	10700	120	11003
15	10207	68	10701	121	11004
16	10208	69	10702	122	11005
17	10209	70	10703	123	11006
18	10210	71	10704	124	11007
19	10211	72	10705	125	11099
20	10212	73	10706	126	20000

21	10213	74	10707	127	20100
22	10214	75	10708	128	20101
23	10215	76	10709	129	20102
24	10216	77	10799	130	20103
25	10217	78	10800	131	20200
26	10218	79	10801	132	20300
27	10219	80	10802	133	20400
28	10220	81	10803	134	20500
29	10299	82	1080400	135	20600
30	10300	83	1080401	136	20601
31	10301	84	1080402	137	20602
32	10302	85	1080403	138	20603
33	10303	86	1080404	139	20699
34	10304	87	1080405	140	20700
35	10305	88	1080406	141	20800
36	10399	89	1080407	142	20900
37	10400	90	1080408	143	29900
38	10500	91	1080409	144	30000
39	10501	92	1080410	145	30100
40	10502	93	1080411	146	30200
41	10503	94	1080412	147	30300
42	10504	95	1080500	148	30301
43	10505	96	1080501	149	30302
44	10506	97	1080502	150	39900
45	10507	98	1080503	151	40000
46	10508	99	10899	152	40100
47	10599	100	10900	153	40101
48	10600	101	10901	154	40102
49	10601	102	10902	155	40200
50	10602	103	1090300	156	50000
51	10603	104	1090301	157	50100
52	10604	105	1090302	158	50200
53	10605	106	1090303		

2.3.6 Controlled list: Library of Congress Classification Scheme

Identifier	Type
1	A -- GENERAL WORKS
2	B -- PHILOSOPHY. PSYCHOLOGY. RELIGION
3	BD - Speculative philosophy
4	BF - Psychology
5	BJ - Ethics
6	BL - Religion
7	BP - Islam
8	BR - Christianity
9	C - AUXILIARY SCIENCES OF HISTORY
10	D -- HISTORY OF EUROPE, ASIA, AFRICA, AND OCEANIA
11	D – History (General)
12	DA – History of Great Britain
13	DC – History of France
14	DD – History of Germany
15	DJK – History of Eastern Europe (General)
16	DK – History of Russia, Former Soviet Republics, Poland
17	DS – History of Asia
18	DT – History of Africa
19	E-F – HISTORY: AMERICA
20	G – GEOGRAPHY. ANTHROPOLOGY. RECREATION
21	G - Geography
22	GF – Human ecology
23	GV – Sports and recreation
24	H – SOCIAL SCIENCES
25	H – Social sciences (General)
26	HA - Statistics
27	HB – Economic theory. Demography
28	HC – Economic history and conditions
29	HD – Industries. Land use. Labour
30	HE – Transportation and communications
31	HF - Commerce

32	HG – Finance
33	HJ – Public finance
34	HM – Sociology (General)
35	HN – Social history and conditions. Social problems. Social reform
36	HQ – Gender, Age, Social and intimate relationships
37	HT – Communities. Class. Race
38	HV – Social and public welfare. Criminology
39	HX - Socialism
40	J – POLITICAL SCIENCE
41	JA – Political science (General)
42	JC – Political theory
43	JF – Political institutions and public administration
44	JK - Political institutions and public administration – United States
45	JL - Political institutions and public administration – Canada, West Indies, Mexico, Central and South America
46	JN - Political institutions and public administration - Europe
47	JQ - Political institutions and public administration – Asia, Arab countries, Islamic countries, Africa, Oceania
48	JS – Local government. Municipal government
49	JV – Emigration and immigration. International migration
50	JZ – International relations
51	K - LAW
52	K – Law in general. Comparative and uniform law. Jurisprudence
53	KD – Law: United Kingdom and Ireland
54	KF – Law: United States
55	KJ-KK – Law: Europe
56	KZ – Law of nations
57	L - EDUCATION
58	L – Education (General)
59	LA – History of education
60	LB – Theory and practice of education
61	LC – Special aspects of education
62	M - MUSIC
63	N – FINE ARTS
64	P – LANGUAGE, LITERATURE AND MEDIA

65	PN – Literature (General)
66	Q - SCIENCE
67	QA - Mathematics
68	R - MEDICINE
69	R – Medicine (General)
70	RA – Public aspects of medicine
71	RT - Nursing
72	S - AGRICULTURE
73	T - TECHNOLOGY
74	TD – Environmental technology
75	U – MILITARY SCIENCE
76	U – Military science (General)
77	UA – Armies: Organization, distribution, military situation
78	V – NAVAL SCIENCE
79	V – Naval science (General)
80	VA – Navires : Organization, distribution, naval situation
81	Z- Z – BIBLIOGRAPHY. LIBRARY SCIENCE. INFORMATION RESOURCES

2.3.7 Controlled list: APA PsycINFO Classification

Identifier	Type
1	2100 General Psychology
2	2140 History & Systems
3	2200 Psychometrics & Statistics & Methodology
4	2220 Tests & Testing
5	2221 Sensory & Motor Testing
6	2222 Developmental Scales & Schedules
7	2223 Personality Scales & Inventories
8	2224 Clinical Psychological Testing
9	2225 Neuropsychological Assessment
10	2226 Health Psychology Testing
11	2227 Educational Measurement
12	2228 Occupational & Employment Testing
13	2229 Consumer Opinion & Attitude Testing

14	2240 Statistics & Mathematics
15	2260 Research Methods & Experimental Design
16	2300 Human Experimental Psychology
17	2320 Sensory Perception
18	2323 Visual Perception
19	2326 Auditory & Speech Perception
20	2330 Motor Processes
21	2340 Cognitive Processes
22	2343 Learning & Memory
23	2346 Attention
24	2360 Motivation & Emotion
25	2380 Consciousness States
26	2390 Parapsychology
27	2400 Animal Experimental & Comparative Psychology
28	2420 Learning & Motivation
29	2440 Social & Instinctive Behavior
30	2500 Physiological Psychology & Neuroscience
31	2510 Genetics
32	2520 Neuropsychology & Neurology
33	2530 Electrophysiology
34	2540 Physiological Processes
35	2560 Psychophysiology
36	2580 Psychopharmacology
37	2600 Psychology & the Humanities
38	2610 Literature & Fine Arts
39	2630 Philosophy
40	2700 Communication Systems
41	2720 Linguistics & Language & Speech
42	2750 Mass Media Communications
43	2800 Developmental Psychology
44	2820 Cognitive & Perceptual Development
45	2840 Psychosocial & Personality Development
46	2860 Gerontology

47	2900 Social Processes & Social Issues
48	2910 Social Structure & Organization
49	2920 Religion
50	2930 Culture & Ethnology
51	2950 Marriage & Family
52	2953 Divorce & Remarriage
53	2956 Childrearing & Child Care
54	2960 Political Processes & Political Issues
55	2970 Sex Roles & Women's Issues
56	2980 Sexual Behavior & Sexual Orientation
57	2990 Drug & Alcohol Usage (Legal)
58	3000 Social Psychology
59	3020 Group & Interpersonal Processes
60	3040 Social Perception & Cognition
61	3100 Personality Psychology
62	3120 Personality Traits & Processes
63	3140 Personality Theory
64	3143 Psychoanalytic Theory
65	3200 Psychological & Physical Disorders
66	3210 Psychological Disorders
67	3211 Affective Disorders
68	3213 Schizophrenia & Psychotic States
69	3215 Neuroses & Anxiety Disorders
70	3217 Personality Disorders
71	3230 Behavior Disorders & Antisocial Behavior
72	3233 Substance Abuse & Addiction
73	3236 Criminal Behavior & Juvenile Delinquency
74	3250 Developmental Disorders & Autism
75	3253 Learning Disorders
76	3256 Mental Retardation
77	3260 Eating Disorders
78	3270 Speech & Language Disorders
79	3280 Environmental Toxins & Health

80	3290 Physical & Somatoform & Psychogenic Disorders
81	3291 Immunological Disorders
82	3293 Cancer
83	3295 Cardiovascular Disorders
84	3297 Neurological Disorders & Brain Damage
85	3299 Vision & Hearing & Sensory Disorders
86	3300 Health & Mental Health Treatment & Prevention
87	3310 Psychotherapy & Psychotherapeutic Counseling
88	3311 Cognitive Therapy
89	3312 Behavior Therapy & Behavior Modification
90	3313 Group & Family Therapy
91	3314 Interpersonal & Client Centered & Humanistic Therapy
92	3315 Psychoanalytic Therapy
93	3340 Clinical Psychopharmacology
94	3350 Specialized Interventions
95	3351 Clinical Hypnosis
96	3353 Self Help Groups
97	3355 Lay & Paraprofessional & Pastoral Counseling
98	3357 Art & Music & Movement Therapy
99	3360 Health Psychology & Medicine
100	3361 Behavioral & Psychological Treatment of Physical Illness
101	3363 Medical Treatment of Physical Illness
102	3365 Promotion & Maintenance of Health & Wellness
103	3370 Health & Mental Health Services
104	3371 Outpatient Services
105	3373 Community & Social Services
106	3375 Home Care & Hospice
107	3377 Nursing Homes & Residential Care
108	3379 Inpatient & Hospital Services
109	3380 Rehabilitation
110	3383 Drug & Alcohol Rehabilitation
111	3384 Occupational & Vocational Rehabilitation
112	3385 Speech & Language Therapy

113	3386 Criminal Rehabilitation & Penology
114	3400 Professional Psychological & Health Personnel Issues
115	3410 Professional Education & Training
116	3430 Professional Personnel Attitudes & Characteristics
117	3450 Professional Ethics & Standards & Liability
118	3470 Impaired Professionals
119	3500 Educational Psychology
120	3510 Educational Administration & Personnel
121	3530 Curriculum & Programs & Teaching Methods
122	3550 Academic Learning & Achievement
123	3560 Classroom Dynamics & Student Adjustment & Attitudes
124	3570 Special & Remedial Education
125	3575 Gifted & Talented
126	3580 Educational/Vocational Counseling & Student Services
127	3600 Industrial & Organizational Psychology
128	3610 Occupational Interests & Guidance
129	3620 Personnel Management & Selection & Training
130	3630 Personnel Evaluation & Job Performance
131	3640 Management & Management Training
132	3650 Personnel Attitudes & Job Satisfaction
133	3660 Organizational Behavior
134	3670 Working Conditions & Industrial Safety
135	3700 Sport Psychology & Leisure
136	3720 Sports
137	3740 Recreation & Leisure
138	3800 Military Psychology
139	3900 Consumer Psychology
140	3920 Consumer Attitudes & Behavior
141	3940 Marketing & Advertising
142	4000 Engineering & Environmental Psychology
143	4010 Human Factors Engineering
144	4030 Lifespace & Institutional Design
145	4050 Community & Environmental Planning

146	4070 Environmental Issues & Attitudes
147	4090 Transportation
148	4100 Intelligent Systems
149	4120 Artificial Intelligence & Expert Systems
150	4140 Robotics
151	4160 Neural Networks
152	4200 Forensic Psychology & Legal Issues
153	4210 Civil Rights & Civil Law
154	4230 Criminal Law & Criminal Adjudication
155	4250 Mediation & Conflict Resolution
156	4270 Crime Prevention
157	4290 Police & Legal Personnel

2.3.8 Controlled list: Game Classification

The starting point for the controlled subject list for the field of game classification was the controlled vocabulary of the Xresearch repository, which is based on the classification of the Economic Science Association (ESA)¹⁴. The existing controlled lists (classifications of ESA, Xresearch, Thesaurus Wirtschaft etc.) proved to be too unstructured for the field of Game Classification for the reuse of (economic) experiments in other contexts. Terms from the areas of methods or content description are mixed up or do not show any relevance. An alternative option was to waive a controlled list for the Game Classification field or allowing a “free input”. However, this seemed to be too confusing for a (interdisciplinary) reuse of data and would unnecessarily complicate systemic research. Therefore, a new controlled list of Game Classification has been developed, which transfers the existing categorization (ESA, Thesaurus Wirtschaft, ISPS Yale¹⁵ etc.) with the help of university courses, current publications and conference programmes in a consistent order. The list was then submitted to experts in experimental economic research and adapted on the basis of their comments and corrections.

Identifier	Descriptor
1	Auctions
2	Bargaining game
3	Battle of the sexes
4	Beauty contest
5	Centipede game
6	Chicken game
7	Combinatorial auction

¹⁴ <https://www.economicsscience.org>

¹⁵ <http://isps.yale.edu/research/data#.VYhfgWM08ik>

8	Common-pool resource game
9	Coordination game
10	Dictator game
11	Dilemma game
12	Dollar auction dilemma
13	Double auction
14	Dutch auction
15	English auction
16	First-price auction
17	Güth-van Damme game
18	Markets
19	Minimum effort game
20	Multi-unit auction
21	Posted offer markets
22	Prisoner's dilemma
23	Private-value auction
24	Public goods game
25	Second-price auction
26	Stag hunt
27	Trust game
28	Ultimatum game
29	Other

2.3.9 Controlled list: Topic Specification

As in Controlled list: Game Classification above the controlled lists of content and scope were also compiled on the basis of existing categorization (ESA, Thesaurus Wirtschaft, ISPS Yale etc.). The list was then submitted to experts and adapted based on their recommendations.

Identifier	Descriptor
1	Altruism
2	Ambiguity
3	Animals
4	Backwards induction / Level k reasoning
5	Beliefs
6	Biology
7	Bounded rationality

8	Charitable giving
9	Communication
10	Competition
11	Cooperation
12	Efficiency
13	Emotions
14	Fairness
15	Finance
16	Framing
17	Gender
18	Group behavior
19	Industrial organization
20	Inequity aversion
21	Institutional design
22	Labor economics / Labor market
23	Learning
24	Macroeconomics
25	Market design
26	Morals
27	Nastyness
28	Neuroeconomics
29	Norms
30	Psychology
31	Public Choice
32	Risk
33	Social preferences
34	Other

2.3.10 Controlled list: Keywords

The controlled list of keywords was compiled on the basis of existing current international publications in the field of experimental economic research. The list consists of the published keywords of the following journals:

- a) Experimental Economics Vol. 17-19 (2014-2016)
- b) Games and Economic Behavior Vol. 91-100 (2015-2016)
- c) Game Theory Vol. 44-45 (2014-2016)

The use of keywords supports the data provider by finding words for his individual keywords on one hand and prevents incorrect spelling on the other.

Id.	Descriptor
1	Abilities
2	Adjacent strategy-proofness
3	Adverse selection
4	Advocacy
5	Affirmative action
6	Agenda manipulation
7	Aggregation rule
8	All-pay auction
9	Altruism
10	Ambiguity aversion
11	Anonymous random matching
12	Assortativity
13	Asymmetric information
14	Auctions
15	Award rules
16	Awareness
17	Bandit problem
18	Bargaining
19	Bargaining theory
20	Bayesian game with infinite type spaces
21	Behavior strategy
22	Behavioral game theory
23	Behavioral mechanism design
24	Behavioral models
25	Best shot
26	Best-response equivalence
27	Blackwell's theorem
28	Bounded perception
29	Bounded rationality
30	Budget balance
31	Centipede games
32	Characterization theorems
33	Charitable giving
34	Cheap talk
35	Choice-based welfare analysis
36	Closed-graph property
37	Cognitive hierarchy
38	Cognitive hierarchy models
39	Collective action
40	Collusion
41	Commitment
42	Common value

Id.	Descriptor
105	First-order assessment
106	Formal bargaining
107	Free riding
108	Fundraising
109	Gambling
110	Generalized cognitive hierarchy
111	Generosity
112	Gift-responsiveness
113	Global games
114	Group contest
115	Guilt aversion
116	Hard leverage
117	Hierarchy
118	Homo moralis
119	Image scoring
120	Imitative dynamics
121	Impartiality
122	Impossibility theorems
123	Incentive compatibility
124	Indirect reciprocity
125	Indivisible objects allocation
126	Inefficiency of equilibria
127	Influence
128	Informal bargaining
129	Information acquisition
130	Information revelation
131	Information search and aggregation
132	Institutions
133	Institutional design
134	Interdependent values
135	Investment game
136	Judgment aggregation
137	Kalai-Smorodinsky
138	Kemeny distance
139	Kemeny sets
140	Knowledge
141	Lab experiments
142	Laboratory experiment
143	Laboratory experiments
144	Large game with traits (LGT)
145	Lead by example
146	Leadership

Id.	Descriptor
209	Performance feedback
210	Persuasion
211	Pigou-Dalton transfers
212	Plurality correspondence
213	Polarization
214	Political representation
215	Polynomials in Bernstein form
216	Population monotonicity
217	Preference aggregation
218	Preference evolution
219	Price controls
220	Price of anarchy
221	Principal agent
222	Principal-agent
223	Principal-agent problem
224	Prisoners' dilemma
225	Private information
226	Probabilistic assignment
227	Procrastination
228	Project selection
229	Prospect theory
230	Psychological games
231	Punishment
232	QRE
233	Quantal response equilibrium
234	R&D
235	Random assignment
236	Random serial dictatorship
237	Reciprocity
238	Reduced-form implementation
239	Rent seeking
240	Repeated games
241	Replicator dynamic
242	Resale
243	Resource dilemma
244	Resource-monotonicity
245	Return policies
246	Risk aversion
247	Risk heterogeneity
248	Risk-sharing
249	Robust mechanism design
250	Saddles

43	Common pool resource
44	Common-value
45	Competence
46	Competition
47	Competitive equilibrium
48	Conditional cooperation
49	Condorcet Jury model
50	Conflict
51	Conflict of interest
52	Contests
53	Continuous strategy space
54	Contract
55	Contract design
56	Convex analysis
57	Convex set
58	Cooperation
59	Cooperative games
60	Coordination
61	Coordination games
62	Core
63	Costly voting
64	Credibility
65	Cutsets
66	Cyclic partition
67	Deadlines
68	Deal-responsiveness
69	Decentralized matching
70	Decision theory
71	Deferred acceptance
72	Deferred-acceptance-algorithm
73	Description-sensitivity
74	Desirability relation
75	Dictator game
76	Disclosure
77	Discrete cheap talk
78	Discrimination
79	Diversity
80	Divide-and-choose
81	Divide-and-Transpose
82	Dominant strategy
83	Donation game
84	Duplication
85	Dynamic decision-making
147	Lebesgue unit interval
148	Legislative bargaining
149	Level-k
150	Level-k model
151	Level-k models
152	Level-m model
153	Limited liability
154	Linear values
155	Logarithmic game
156	Logit equilibrium
157	Long-term advisory relationship
158	Lorenz dominance
159	Loss aversion
160	Lying
161	Many-to-many matching
162	Many-to-one matching with wages
163	Market
164	Markov perfect equilibrium
165	Marriage problems
166	Matching
167	Matching with contracts
168	Mechanism design
169	Median stable matchings
170	Median voter
171	Menu choice
172	Minimax theorem
173	Misrepresentations
174	Mistake monotonicity
175	Mixed strategy equilibrium
176	Morality
177	Multi-dimensional screening
178	Multidistrict elections
179	Multilateral sanctions
180	Multi-period delegation
181	Multiple audiences
182	Multiple equilibria
183	Multiple issues
184	Multiple senders
185	Multitasking
186	Multi-unit auction
187	Naive players
188	Nash equilibrium
189	Nash equilibrium distribution
251	Saturated probability space
252	School choice
253	Search
254	Second-order beliefs
255	Second-price auction with incomplete information
256	Self-serving biases
257	Sender
258	Sender–receiver games
259	Sequential screening
260	Shapley
261	Social choice
262	Social preferences
263	Social pressure
264	Soft leverage
265	Sophisticated players
266	Spanning trees
267	Spatial bargaining
268	Specialization
269	Spiteful preferences
270	Stability
271	Stable systems
272	Status quo rules
273	Strategic communication
274	Strategic information transmission
275	Strategic learning
276	Strategyproofness
277	Strategy-proofness
278	Strong substitutability
279	Subgame perfect ϵ -equilibria
280	Subjective states
281	Submodularity
282	Supermodularity
283	Support function
284	Target
285	Team production
286	The law of aggregate demand
287	Time-inconsistent preferences
288	Tragedy of the commons
289	Trembling hand perfect equilibrium
290	Truncation strategies
291	Trust
292	Trust game
293	Trustworthiness

86	Dynamic games	190	Nash implementation	294	Two-dimensional values
87	Dynamic mechanism design	191	Networks	295	Two-sided matching
88	Dynamic signaling	192	No-envy	296	Unawareness
89	Economic development	193	Noisy reputation	297	Uncertainty
90	Efficiency	194	Non-equilibrium structural models	298	Uncovered set
91	Electoral control	195	Non-segregation	299	Uniform equilibria
92	Endogenous evaluations	196	Non-wastefulness	300	Uniform-price auctions
93	Endogenous status-quo	197	Norm compliance	301	Upper semi-continuous functions
94	Entrepreneurship	198	Observable payoff	302	Value of information
95	Equilibrium selection	199	Ordinal efficiency	303	Vickrey auctions
96	Estimation	200	Ordinal mechanism	304	Voluntary and compulsory voting
97	Evolutionary stability	201	Organization design	305	Voting behavior
98	Experiment	202	Other-regarding preferences	306	Vulnerability-responsiveness
99	Experimental auctions	203	Participation constraint	307	Weakly linear games
100	Experimental economics	204	Participation games	308	Wealth effects
101	Experimentation	205	Partitional equilibria	309	Welfare dominance under preference replacement
102	Experiments	206	Partnerships	310	Welfare loss
103	Externalities	207	Payoff identification	311	Winner's-bid auction
104	Fairness	208	Payoff monotonicity	312	Zero-sum games

2.3.11 Controlled list: Description Type

Controlled list from da|ra Metadata Schema, p. 51, Tab. 4.1.4 (Koch, Akdeniz, Meichsner, Hausstein, & Harzenetter, 2017)

Identifier	Descriptor	Definition
5	Other	Other description information that does not fit into an existing category.

2.3.12 Controlled list: Data Collection Mode

For the field Data Collection Mode, the controlled list of Xresearch was further developed and extended.

Identifier	Descriptor
1	Artefactual Field Experiment
2	Computer Assisted
3	eEg (Electroencephalogram)
4	Electrocardiography (ECG)
5	Electrodermal Activity
6	Electromyography (EMG)
7	Eye Tracking
8	Factorial Survey

9	Field Experiments
10	fMRI
11	Framed Field Experiment
12	Internet
13	Interview, qualitative
14	Interview, quantitative
15	Laboratory Experiment
16	Meta study
17	Natural Field Experiment
18	Pen and Paper
19	Photoplethysmography (PPG)
20	Randomized-Response Technique
21	Split Ballot
22	Mechanical Turk, Amazon
23	Mechanical Turk, RapidWorkers
24	Mechanical Turk, Samasource
25	Mechanical Turk, MicroWorkers
26	Mechanical Turk, ClickWorker
27	Mechanical Turk, ShortTask
28	Mechanical Turk, Other
29	Meta study
30	Natural Field Experiment
31	Pen and Paper
32	Photoplethysmography (PPG)
33	Randomized-Response Technique
34	Split Ballot
35	Other

2.3.13 Controlled list: Laboratory

No.	Name	Uni/Institution	Acronym	Land
1	MGSM Vernon L. Smith Experimental Economics Laboratory	Macquarie University Graduate School of Management		Australia
2	Monash Laboratory for Experimental Economics	Monash University/Monash Business School	MonLEE	Australia
3	Queensland Behavioural Economics lab	Queensland University of Technology	QuBE Lab	Australia
4	Behavioural Business Lab	RMIT University		Australia
5	Adelaide Laboratory for Experimental Economics	University of Adelaide	ADLab	Australia
6	Experimental Economics Laboratory	University of Melbourne	E ² MU Lab	Australia
7	UNSW Business School Experimental Research Laboratory	University of New South Wales	BIZLab	Australia
8	Behavioural Research Laboratory	University of Sydney		Australia
9	UTS Behavioural Laboratory	University of Technology Sydney		Australia

10	Aton Experimental Economics Laboratory		AEELab	Australia
11	Max Jung Lab for Experimental Economics	University of Graz		Austria
12	Innsbruck EconLab	University of Innsbruck		Austria
13	Vienna Center for Experimental Economics	University of Vienna	VCEE	Austria
14	Experimental Lab of the Center for Interuniversity Research and Analysis of Organizations	Center for Interuniversity Research and Analysis of Organizations	CIRANO Lab	Canada
15	Laval Experimental Economics Laboratory	Laval University	LEEL	Canada
16	McMaster Experimental Economics Laboratory	McMaster University	McEEL	Canada
17	Experimental Lab of the Centre for Research in Adaptive Behaviour in Economics	Simon Fraser University/Centre for Research in Adaptive Behaviour in Economics	CRABE Lab	Canada
18	Behavioral Research Lab of the Department of Marketing, Business Economics and Law	University of Alberta		Canada
19	Experimental Lab at the Vancouver School of Economics	University of British Columbia	ELVSE	Canada
20	Calgary Behavioural & Experimental Economics Lab	University of Calgary	CBEEL	Canada
21	Smith Experimental Economics Research Center	Shanghai Jiaotong University		China
22	Finance and Economics Experimental Laboratory	Xiamen University	FEEL	China
23	Experimental Social Science Laboratory	Zhejiang University		China
24	Laboratory for Experimental Economics	University of Economics in Prague	LEE	Czech Republic
25	Cognition and Behavior Lab	Aarhus University	COBELab	Denmark
26	Centre for Experimental Economics	University of Copenhagen	CEE	Denmark
27	PCRC Decision Making Laboratory	University of Turku		Finnland
28	Laboratory for Experimentation in Social Sciences and Behavioral Analysis	Burgundy School of Business	LESSAC	France
29	Behavioral Lab	INSEAD-Sorbonne University		France
30	Behavioral and Experimental Economics Research Unit	Toulouse School of Economics / IAST		France
31	Grenoble Applied Economics Lab	University Grenoble Alpes / Grenoble INP / CNRS / INRA	GAEL	France
32	GATE Lab	University Lyon 2		France
33	Montpellier Laboratory for Theoretic and Applied Economics	University of Montpellier 1	LAMETA / LEEM	France
34	Parisian Experimental Economics Laboratory	University of Paris 1	LEEP	France
35	Social Sciences Experimental Laboratory	University of Rennes 1	LABEX-EM	France
36	Bureau for Economic Theory and Applications	University of Strasbourg / University of Lorraine / CNRS	BETA Lab	France
37	EXperimental Economics at Clausthal University of Technology	Clausthal University of Technology	ExECUTE	Germany
38	Experimental Lab of the Institute of Entrepreneurial and Behavioral Decision Making	Humboldt University Berlin		Germany
39	Karlsruhe Decision & Design Lab	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	KD2-Lab	Germany
40	Lab for Experimental Economics	Ruhr University Bochum	RUBex	Germany
41	Lab for Economic Experiments	Technical University Berlin		Germany
42	Bonn Laboratory for Experimental Economics	University of Bonn	BonnE-conLab	Germany
43	Cologne Laboratory of Economic Research	University of Cologne	CLER	Germany
44	Essen Laboratory for Experimental Economics	University of Duisburg-Essen	ELFE	Germany
45	Düsseldorf Institute for Competition Economics Lab for Experimental Economics	University of Düsseldorf/Düsseldorf Institute for Competition Economics	DICELab	Germany
46	Laboratory for Experimental Economics	University of Erfurt	eLab	Germany
47	WISO-Research Lab	University of Hamburg		Germany
48	Alfred-Weber-Institute Experimental Laboratory	University of Heidelberg	AWI-Lab	Germany
49	Experimental Lab of the Chair for Empirical and Experimental Economics	University of Jena		Germany

50	Experimental Lab of the Chair of Innovation, Competition Policy and New Institutional Economics	University of Kiel		Germany
51	Lakelab (<i>des Thurgauer Wirtschaftsinstituts an der Universität Konstanz</i>)	University of Konstanz/Thurgau Institute of Economics		Germany
52	Leipziger Experimentallabors für Sozialwissenschaften	University of Leipzig	LEx	Germany
53	Magdeburg Experimental Laboratory of Economic Research	University of Magdeburg	MaXLab	Germany
54	Mannheim Laboratory for Experimental Economics	University of Mannheim	mLab	Germany
55	Munich Experimental Laboratory for Economic and Social Sciences	University of Munich	MELESSA	Germany
56	Experimental Lab of the Center for Social Sciences Research Methods	University of Oldenburg	MSW-Lab	Germany
57	Laboratory for Economic Research	University of Osnabrück	LaER	Germany
58	Business and Economic Research Laboratory	University of Paderborn	BaER-Lab	Germany
59	PAULA Experimental Laboratory	University of Passau	PAULA	Germany
60	Potsdam Laboratory for Economic Experiments	University of Potsdam	PLEx	Germany
61	Energy and Environmental Policy Laboratory	University of Piraeus		Greece
62	Vernon Smith Center for Experimental Economics	Francisco Marroquin University		Guatemala
63	Experimental Economics Laboratory	City University of Hong Kong		Hong Kong
64	Experimental Economics Laboratory	Ben-Gurion University of the Negev		Israel
65	RatioLab - Interactive Decision Laboratory	Hebrew University of Jerusalem		Israel
66	Laboratory of Behavioral Research	Technion - Israel Institute of Technology		Israel
67	Bocconi Experimental Laboratory for the Social Sciences	Bocconi University	BELSS	Italy
68	Center for Experimental Research in Management and Economics	Ca' Foscari University of Venice	CERME	Italy
69	Centro di Economia Sperimentale a Roma Est	LUISS Guido Carli	CESARE	Italy
70	Bologna Laboratory for Experiments in Social Science	University of Bologna	BLESS	Italy
71	Experimental and Simulative Economics Laboratory	University of Eastern Piedmont	AL.EX	Italy
72	Behavioural and Experimental Economics Lab	University of Florence	BEELab	Italy
73	Behavioral and Experimental Economics Research Group	University of Milano Bicocca		Italy
74	Laboratorio di Ricerca in Economia Sperimentale di Salerno	University of Salerno	LabESS	Italy
75	Laboratory of Experimental Economics	University of Siena / Interuniversity Center for Experimental Economics	LabSi	Italy
76	Cognitive and Experimental Economics Laboratory	University of Trento	CEEL	Italy
77	Economics Laboratory of the Research Center for Behavioral Economics	Osaka University / MEXT		Japan
78	Busara Center for Behavioral Economics			Kenya
79	ESE EconLab	Erasmus School of Economics		Netherlands
80	Behavioral and Experimental Economics Lab	Maastrich University	BEElab	Netherlands
81	Decision Lab / VISA Skills Lab	Radboud University		Netherlands
82	CentERlab	Tilburg University		Netherlands
83	Center for Research in Experimental Economics and Political Decision Making	University of Amsterdam	CREED	Netherlands
84	Experimental Laboratory for Sociology and Economics	Utrecht University	ELSE	Netherlands
85	New Zealand Experimental Economics Laboratory	University of Canterbury	NZEEL	New Zealand
86	Centre for Experimental Studies and Research	Norwegian Business School	CESAR	Norway
87	The Choice Lab	Norwegian School of Economics		Norway

88	Oslo Economics Laboratory	University of Oslo	OEconLab	Norway
89	Experimental Economics Laboratory	University of Warsaw		Poland
90	Research Unit in Behavioural Economics and Neuroeconomics	University of Cape Town	RUBEN	South Africa
91	Sogang Experimental Economics Laboratory	Sogang University	SEE Lab	South Korea
92	Experimental Economics Laboratory	Autonomous University of Barcelona/Institute of Economic Analysis		Spain
93	Madrid Laboratory of Experimental Economics	Autonomous University of Madrid	MADLEE	Spain
94	Laboratory of Experimental Economics	Jaume I University	LEE	Spain
95	Laboratory for Experimental Business and Economics	Pablo Olavide University of Seville	LEXBE	Spain
96	Behavioral Sciences Laboratory	Pompeu Fabra University Barcelona	BESLab/LEE X	Spain
97	Laboratory for Theoretical and Experimental Economics	University of Alicante	LaTeX	Spain
98	Granada Lab of Behavioral Economics	University of Granada	GLOBE	Spain
99	Bilbao Laboratory of Experimental Analysis	University of the Basque Country	Bilbao LABEAN	Spain
100	Laboratory for Research in Experimental and Behavioural Economics	University of Valencia	LINEEX	Spain
101	JEDI Lab	Linköping University		Sweden
102	Experimental Economics Laboratory	University of Gothenburg		Sweden
103	Laboratory for Experimental and Behavioral Economics	University of Zurich		Switzerland
104	Taiwan Social Science Experimental Laboratory	National Taiwan University	TASSEL	Taiwan
105	Bilgi Economics Lab of Istanbul	Istanbul Bilgi University	BELIS	Turkey
106	Behavioral and Experimental Lab	Middle East Technical University		Turkey
107	Lancaster Experimental Economics Laboratory	Lancaster University	LExEL	UK
108	Behavioral ResearchLab	London School of Economics and Political Science		UK
109	ExpPreSS Laboratory of Experimental Research in Social Sciences	Royal Holloway University of London		UK
110	Centre for Economic Learning and Social Evolution	University College London / Economic and Social Research Council	ELSE	UK
111	Scottish Experimental Economics Laboratory	University of Aberdeen	SEEL	UK
112	Centre for Behavioural and Experimental Social Science	University of East Anglia	CBESS	UK
113	Finance and Economics Experimental Laboratory at Exeter	University of Exeter	FEELE	UK
114	Centre for Decision Research and Experimental Economics	University of Nottingham	CeDEx	UK
115	Nuttfield Centre for Experimental Social Science	University of Oxford / Nuttfield College	CESS	UK
116	Oxford Experimental Lab	University of Oxford / Saïd Business School	OXlab	UK
117	Social Sciences Experimental Laboratory	University of Southampton		UK
118	Decision Research at Warwick	University of Warwick	DR@W	UK
119	Centre for Experimental Economics	University of York	EXEC Lab	UK
120	Social Science Experimental Laboratory	New York University of Abu Dhabi	SSEL	United Arab Emirates
121	Appalachian Experimental Economics Laboratory	Appalachian State University	AppEEL	USA
122	Brown University Social Science Experimental Laboratory	Brown University	BUSSEL	USA
123	Social Science Experimental Laboratory / Laboratory for Experimental Economics and Political Science	California Institute of Technology	SSEL / EEPS (Plott Lab)	USA
124	Dynamic Decision Making Laboratory	Carnegie Mellon University	DDMLab	USA
125	Economic Science Institute's Laboratory for	Chapman University		USA

	Experimental Economics			
126	Center for Neuroeconomic Studies	Claremont Graduate University	CNS	USA
127	Columbia Experimental Laboratory in the Social Sciences	Columbia University	CELSS	USA
128	Debra Paget and Jeffrey Berg Business Simulation Lab	Cornell University		USA
129	Lab for Experimental Economics and Decision Research	Cornell University	LEEDR	USA
130	XS/FS Lab	Florida State University		USA
131	The Interdisciplinary Center for Economic Science	George Mason University	ICES	USA
132	Dean's Behavioral Economics Laboratory	Georgia State University	DBEL	USA
133	Experimental Economics Center	Georgia State University	ExCEN	USA
134	Harvard Decision Science Laboratory	Harvard University		USA
135	Computer Lab for Experimental Research	Harvard University/Harvard Business School	CLER	USA
136	Interdisciplinary Experimental Laboratory	Indiana University Bloomington	IELab	USA
137	Experimental Economics Laboratory	Loyola Marymount University	EconLab	USA
138	Center for Experimental Social Science	New York University	CESS	USA
139	Experimental Economics Laboratory	Ohio State University		USA
140	Laboratory for Economics, Management and Auctions	Pennsylvania State University		USA
141	Princeton Laboratory for Experimental Social Science	Princeton University	PLESS	USA
142	Vernon Smith Experimental Economics Laboratory	Purdue University	VSEEL	USA
143	Behavioral Research Laboratory	Rice University		USA
144	Gregory Wachtler Experimental Economics Laboratory of the Center for Economic Behavior, Institutions and Design	Rutgers University		USA
145	Laboratory for Research in Experimental Economics	Southern Methodist University	LREE	USA
146	Laboratory for Experimental Economics	St. Lawrence University		USA
147	Center for Behavioral Political Economy's Decision Experiment Lab	Stony Brook University		USA
148	Economic Research Lab	Texas A&M University	ERL	USA
149	Experimental Economics Lab	University of Alaska Anchorage		USA
150	Decision Behavior Laboratory / Economic Science Lab	University of Arizona	DBL / ESL	USA
151	Behavioral Business Research Lab	University of Arkansas	BBRL	USA
152	Experimental Social Science Laboratory	University of California Berkley	XLab	USA
153	Experimental Social Science Laboratory	University of California Irvine	ESSL	USA
154	California Social Science Experimental Laboratory	University of California Los Angeles	CASSEL	USA
155	Behavioral Research Lab	University of California Riverside	AGSM Lab	USA
156	Economics Laboratory	University of California San Diego		USA
157	Experimental and Behavioral Economics Laboratory	University of California Santa Barbara	EBEL	USA
158	Learning and Experimental Economics Projects	University of California Santa Cruz	LEEPS	USA
159	Behavioral Research Lab	University of Central Florida		USA
160	Center for Experimental and Applied Economics	University of Delaware		USA
161	Laboratory for Computer-Mediated Experiments and the Study of Culture	University of Hawaii		USA
162	Behavioral Research Lab	University of Kentucky / Gatton College of Business and Economics		USA
163	Experimental Economics Laboratory	University of Maryland	EEL-UMD	USA
164	Cleve E. Willis Experimental Economics Laboratory and Endowment	University of Massachusetts Amherst		USA

165	Social and Behavioral Sciences Laboratory	University of Minnesota		USA
166	Mississippi Experimental Research Laboratory	University of Mississippi	MERL	USA
167	Wharton Behavioral Lab	University of Pennsylvania		USA
168	Pittsburgh Experimental Economics Lab	University of Pittsburgh	PEEL	USA
169	Policy Simulation Lab	University of Rhode Island		USA
170	Judith A. and Robert E. Griffin Experimental Economics Laboratory	University of Southern Indiana		USA
171	Center For Behavioral and Experimental Economic Science	University of Texas at Dallas	CBEES	USA
172	Missouri Social Science Experimental Lab	University of Washington in St. Louis	MISSEL	USA
173	Experimental Laboratory for Economics and Business Research	Virginia Commonwealth University		USA
174	Economics Lab	Williams College		USA
175	Consumer Decision Making Lab	Yale School of Management	SOM Lab	USA

2.3.14 Controlled list: Experimental Software

Identifier	Type
1	z-Tree
2	oTree
3	classEx
4	Veconlab
5	Qualtrics
6	LIONESS Lab

2.3.15 Controlled list: Professional Status of Participants

Identifier	Descriptor
1	Artificial intelligence (AI)
2	Children: Kindergarten age
3	Employees
4	Managers / Employees in managerial position
5	Pensioners
6	School children
7	Self-employed
8	Students
9	Students: Economics
10	Students: Humanities
11	Students: Law
12	Students: Psychology
13	Students: STEM / MINT
14	Students: Social Sciences
15	Unemployed
16	Others

2.3.16 Controlled list: Currency

Identifier	Type	Definition
1	Euro	Euro (€)
2	US-Dollar	US Dollar (\$)

2.3.17 Controlled list: Experimental Stimulus

Identifier	Descriptor
1	Auditory
2	Drug / medical treatment
3	Haptic
4	Olfactory
5	Visual
6	Other

2.3.18 Controlled list: Design decisions

Id.	Descriptor
1	Anonymity: No anonymity
2	Anonymity: Single-blind
3	Anonymity: Double-blind
4	Anonymity: Triple-blind
5	Deception
6	Direct response method / straight mode
7	Feedback
8	Finitely long games / fixed end round
9	Imperfect information
10	Infinitely long games
11	Matching Method: Partners design
12	Matching Method: Strangers design
13	Matching Method: Perfect strangers design
14	Multi-stage game
15	No-feedback
16	One shot game / single play
17	Perfect information
18	Repeated game / repeat play
19	Restart
20	Sequential

21	Simultaneous
22	Single stage game
23	Stage game
24	Strategy method / level playing field mode
24	Other

2.3.19 Controlled list: Interaction

Identifier	Descriptor
1	Animal – Human
2	Human – Computer
3	Human – Human
4	Others

2.3.20 Controlled list: Incentive

Identifier	Descriptor
1	Cash payment immediately after experiment
2	Course credit
3	Nothing
4	Payment with delay
5	Others

2.3.21 Controlled list: Type of Data

Identifier	Type
1	Dataset
2	Codebook
3	Instructions
4	Program code (and export of the experiment)
5	Screenshots
6	Characteristics of the participants
7	Statistics
8	Other

2.3.22 Controlled list: Document Type¹⁶

Identifier	Type	Definition
1	Working Paper	A preliminary scientific or technical paper released for input and critique (most often grey literature).
2	Article	A nonfictional literary composition that forms an independent part of a publication e. g. in a journal or magazine.
3	Report	A written account of something that one has observed, heard, done, or investigated and that is prepared on ad hoc, periodic, recurring, regular, or as required basis.
4	Book / Monograph	A set of written, printed, illustrated or blank sheets that conjoin into one literary work. A monograph is a non-serial publication on a single subject or an aspect of a subject, usually by a single author.
5	Manuscript	A book, document, or other composition written by hand as well as text submitted to the publisher or printer in preparation for publication, regardless of the format.
6	Reference Book	A book, such as a dictionary or encyclopedia, to which one can refer for authoritative information and intended primarily for consultation rather than for consecutive reading.
7	Review	An evaluation of e. g. a publication, theory or synthesis of research on a topic at that moment in time.
8	Series	A (regularly) sequence of publications like books or journal articles that have (roughly) the same subject.
9	Journal	Newspaper or magazine that deals with a particular subject or professional activity and that is issued in a regular cycle.
10	Newspaper	A printed publication (usually issued daily or weekly) consisting of folded unstapled sheets and containing news, articles, advertisements and correspondence.

2.3.23 Controlled list: Estimated Effects

Identifier	Descriptor
1	Main effects and interaction effects
2	Main effects only

2.3.24 Controlled list Construction Vignette Sample

Identifier	Descriptor
1	Confounded D-efficient design
2	Confounded fractional factorial designs
3	D-efficient designs
4	Fractional factorial designs
5	Random designs

2.3.25 Controlled list Presentation Order

Identifier	Descriptor
1	Fixed order
2	Random order

¹⁶ Koch, U., Akdeniz, E., Meichsner, J., Hausstein, B., & Harzenetter, K. (2017). da|ra Metadata Schema. Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Social and Economic Data. Version 4.0. GESIS Papers 2017|25. Köln: GESIS. doi: 10.4232/10.mdsdoc.4.0

2.3.26 Controlled list Vignette Presentation

Identifier	Descriptor
1	Bulletpoints
2	Image/Illustration
3	Table
4	Text
5	Text marked (e.g., bold, italic)

2.3.27 Controlled list Answer Scale Rating

Identifier	Descriptor
1	Amount
2	Categorical non ordered
3	Categorical ordered
4	Dichotomous
5	Magnitude scaling
6	Percentage
7	Point scale
8	Other